

Leveraging Machine Learning and Street View Imagery to Study the association between social inequalities and visual walkability in the South Africa Context

Lingshan Li^{*1}, Stephen Law^{†1}

¹UCL, Department of Geography

GISRUK 2024

Summary

Walkability is crucial for improving urban sustainability. Most studies on walkability focused in developed countries, while only a few studies have been conducted in the Global South due partially to limited data availability. To address the limitation, this research calculated visual walkability using Street View Imagery and computer vision techniques in Johannesburg, South Africa, and then explored the relationship between social-economic indicators and walkability. The results offer insights on the social and spatial inequality of walkability in the South African context.

KEYWORDS: transportation and urban planning, machine learning, computer vision, visual walkability, social inequalities

1.0 Background

Ever since the launch of the national initiative "The Campaign to Make America Walkable" in 1998, the concept of walkable communities has become a guiding principle within various urban planning and design activities across the US (Zhu et al., 2013). This trend has also gained momentum and extended its influence to numerous Western nations (Zhou et al., 2019). Between 2009 and 2018, 75.3% of walkability research focused on North America, Europe, and Asia.

Only a few studies have been conducted in the Global South, reflecting limited attention to walkability in developing countries (Arellana et al., 2019). This can be partially attributed to limited technologies in data collection (Zhou et al., 2019). Advances in Google Street View GSV analysis and computer vision can be used to address this challenge, as it offers an objective method for assessing the subjective perception of the built environment (Lu et al., 2018; Yin&Wang, 2016).

Moreover, significant social and spatial inequalities still remain today that continually deepen poverty and exclusion in Post-Apartheid South Africa (Lloyd et al., 2021). For example, the poor who suffered racially discriminatory restrictions have unequal access to public transport (Gevisser, 2014, p.20). To explore the extent such inequality might also exist in walking amenity/infrastructure, we aim to leverage machine learning and GSV to estimate visual walkability for the city of Johannesburg in South Africa. Subsequently, we will analyze the connection between visual walkability and socio-economic indicators, aiming to gain a deeper understanding of the social and spatial inequalities in the city.

2.0 Datasets

Johannesburg was chosen as the study area. The street network (**Figure 1**) was extracted from OpenStreetMap (OSM). The locations were determined using the geographic median of the street edge between two junctions, resulting in a total of 310,098 street sites. 50 street sites from each ward in

* lingshan.li.22@ucl.ac.uk

† stephen.law@ucl.ac.uk

Johannesburg (130 wards in total) were selected randomly to create a subset of 6,500 sample points.

Figure 1 Sampling procedures. From left to right; get street network, its median and take 50 samples from each Ward.

Street view imagery was then collected for each sample point using GSV API. Three images were captured in one street site to cover 360° view of the urban environment (**Figure 2**). After image cleaning, 15,600 GSV images (image size 640x640) were used for calculating visual walkability.

Figure 2 Example of a Google Street View Panorama

A number of socio-economic indicators (**Table 1**) were included to study the relationship between social inequalities and visual walkability. We selected SAIMD 2011[‡] because it reflects social inequality linked to deprivation in Post-Apartheid South Africa (Noble et al., 2013). The lag of the census data is a limitation of the study. Nonetheless, this is the most recent data to describe socio-economic characteristics at sub-municipality levels in South Africa (Noble et al., 2013).

[‡] South African Index of Multiple Deprivation 2011 at ward level (unpublished data). Provided by Noble, M., SASPRI.

Multiple Deprivations	Definition
Material Deprivation Score (0-100)	It assesses access to essential items for an adequate living standard at a ward level (e.g., refrigerator, cell phone, radio, or television).
Employment Deprivation Score (0-100)	It assesses joblessness among working-age individuals, including discouraged workers, about the labor force.
Education Deprivation Score (0-100)	It measures limited educational qualifications in adults (18-64).
Living Environment Deprivation Score (0-100)	It assesses the extent to which individuals face poor living conditions in their immediate environment (e.g., water supply, sanitation facilities, and electricity for lighting).

*Note: Within a domain of multiple deprivations, the higher the score, the more deprived the ward.

Table 1 Multiple deprivations and their definitions in SAIMD 2011 (Noble et al., 2013)

3.0 Methodology

To calculate visual walkability, we borrow from the integrated visual walkability model (IVW) proposed by Zhou et al. (2019). **Figure 3** illustrates the overall workflow.

Figure 3 Methodological workflow

3.1 Physical Features Detection: SegFormer

Different from Zhou et al (2019), we selected SegFormer, an efficient semantic segmentation framework (**Figure 4**), that combines a Transformer-encoder and an MLP-decoder for pixel-wise classification (Xie et al., 2021), due to its suitability in recognizing built environment features. The SegFormer model was pretrained on the ADE20K dataset. Segmentation results in each GSV image are expressed as ratios of pixels for specific categories. **Figure 5** shows an example of the semantic segmentation which was qualitatively checked.

Figure 4 The SegFormer framework (Xie et al. 2021)

(a). Segmentation Categories of SegFormer

(b) Display of results of SegFormer

Figure 5 Display of categories of street features and segmentation results of SegFormer

3.2 Calculation of Integrated Visual Walkability (IVW) Index

The IVW framework (Zhou et al., 2019) as illustrated in **Figure 6**, offers a valuable tool for calculation of built environment features using computer vision to quantify psychological and subjective comfort levels among pedestrians. Definition of IVW and four sub-indicators is introduced in **Table 2**, which are calculated based on the ratios of pixels obtained by SegFormer using the segmentation categories in Figure 5(a) as parameters. Considering minor variations in the central visual field have little impact on pedestrian perceptions, and segmentation accuracy directly affects the sub-indicator values. The values of IVW have been reclassified into five levels as shown in **Table 3** and **Table 4** (Lu, Haworth and Wang, 2021). The value of IVW ranges from 20 to 100 where higher IVW refers to higher quality of the built environment for pedestrians from the view of visual psychology.

Figure 6 IVW framework (Zhou et al., 2019)

Indicators	Definition	Formula	Explanation
Psychological Greenery	The degree to which the visibility of street vegetation can impact pedestrian psychological feelings.	$G_i = \frac{\sum_1^3 T_n}{3 \times Sum}$	T_n is the total tree pixel number;
Visual Crowdedness	The degree to which the visibility of obstacles can impact pedestrian experiences.	$C_i = \frac{\sum_1^3 C_n}{3 \times Sum}$	C_n is the total obstacle pixel number;
Outdoor Enclosure	How the room-like outdoor space is (the proportion of vertical objects to horizontal elements).	$S_i = \frac{\sum_1^3 B_n + \sum_1^3 T_n}{\sum_1^3 P_n + \sum_1^3 R_n + \sum_1^3 F_n}$	B_n is the total building pixel number;
Visual Pavement	Psychological effect of the proportion of road and pavement on pedestrian experience.	$D_i = \frac{\sum_1^3 P_n + \sum_1^3 F_n}{\sum_1^3 R_n}$	P_n is the total pavement pixel number;
IVW	Integrated Visual Walkability Index.	$IVW = 5 \times (G_{level} + C_{level} + S_{level} + D_{level})$	R_n is the total road pixel number;
			F_n is the total fence pixel number;
			Sum is the total pixel number.

Table 2 Indicators and their definition, formula, and explanation (Zhou et al., 2019)

	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
G_i	[0, 0.070)	[0.070, 0.127)	[0.127, 0.175)	[0.175, 0.228)	[0.228, +∞)
Sample					
C_i	[0.574, +∞)	[0.413, 0.574)	[0.286, 0.413)	[0.169, 0.286)	[0, 0.169)
Sample	-	-	-		
S_i	[0, 0.800) ∪ [2.864, +∞)	[0.800, 1.063) ∪ [2.210, 2.864)	[1.063, 1.213) ∪ [1.884, 2.210)	[1.213, 1.350) ∪ [1.656, 1.884)	[1.350, 1.656)
Sample					
D_i	[0, 0.480) ∪ [4.000, +∞)	[0.480, 0.650) ∪ [3.007, 4.000)	[0.650, 0.806) ∪ [2.137, 3.007)	[0.806, 0.953) ∪ [1.707, 2.137)	[0.953, 1.707)
Sample					

Table 3 Sample images and classification of sub-indicators at different levels

Level Classification	IVW Score	Indication
Level 1	0-35	Low quality visual environment for walking
Level 2	35-55	Relatively low quality visual environment for walking
Level 3	55-70	Moderate quality visual environment for walking
Level 4	70-80	Relatively high quality visual environment for walking
Level 5	80-100	High quality visual environment for walking

Table 4 IVW Score at different levels (Zhou et al., 2019).

3.3 Spatial Regression between Social Inequalities and IVW

In order to study the association between IVW and social inequalities, we regressed each socio-economic indicator with the IVW index. Due to observed spatial patterns in socio-economic features

(Noble et al., 2013) and walkability scores (Zhou et al., 2019), a spatial lag regression model (Equation.1) with a Queen neighborhood weight matrix was estimated. More formally,

$$Y = \alpha + \beta X + \lambda W_Y + e \quad (1)$$

where Y is the dependent variable (i.e., IVW); X is the explanatory variable (i.e., socio-economic indicators); W_Y is the spatial matrix; β and λ are coefficients; α is a scalar variable; and e is the error term (Darmofal, 2015).

4.0 Results and discussion

4.1 User Study

To begin, we first validated the proposed IVW model by asking Geography students to rate (n=260) street sites on a scale from level 1 to level 5 for subjective scoring. Spearman's rank analysis revealed a significant, moderate positive association between calculated IVW and evaluators' subjective scoring ($\rho = 0.4, P < 0.01$), emphasizing the model's potential to reflect pedestrians' visual walkability. See **Figure 8** for an example of IVW across different levels. Due to time constraints, only four evaluators participated in subjective scoring. Inviting more evaluators in the future may lead to more robust results.

Figure 8 Street views with different levels of visual walkability

4.2 Spatial Patterns of IVW

The spatial patterns of IVW, sub-indicators, and total population at ward level are shown in **Figure 7**. It shows that IVW varies significantly between the wards around the city center (within the blue circle of Figure 7 (a)) and the wards in the surrounding areas. In the city center, IVW is relatively high due to a lower population density and abundant greenery, which contribute to a positive visual urban landscape. Conversely, most wards outside the city center can be classified as underdeveloped regions, scoring lower in walkability. These wards lack adequate pedestrian facilities, have limited green spaces, and limited outdoor enclosure. On a city-wide scale, there are few obstacles (e.g., vehicles) on the streets, and there is a shortage of pedestrian-friendly infrastructure. It evidences a critical challenge in Johannesburg: there are spatial inequalities in traffic regulations, which might be prioritising the needs of the wealthy minority while overlooking the more vulnerable and numerous poor residents (Wood, 2022).

Figure 7 Distribution of average IVW indices, four sub-indicators, and total population in each ward

However, Figure 7 (d), (e), (f) showed that there are no significant differences in the corresponding indicators across Johannesburg at ward level, more specific spatial patterns need to be further explored (e.g. at street level).

4.3 Spatial Regression Results

IVW demonstrates significant negative correlations with all deprivation scores at the ward level, with education deprivation showing the strongest association ($p < 0.05$), as shown in **Table 5**. This indicates that disadvantaged wards tend to suffer from additional lower visual walkability, while wealthier residents in less deprived wards with higher education levels experience higher visual walkability. This informed that future transport policy could prioritize the needs of more deprived wards.

Variables	Regression Equation	R^2
Material Deprivation	$Y = -0.096^{**}X + 43.946^{**} + 0.013^{**}W_Y$	0.18 ^{**}
Employment Deprivation	$Y = -0.220^{**}X + 49.382^{**} + 0.006^*W_Y$	0.66 [*]
Education Deprivation	$Y = -0.460^{**}X + 47.708^{**} + 0.008^*W_Y$	0.37 [*]
Living Environment Deprivation	$Y = -0.074^{**}X + 42.569^{**} + 0.013^{**}W_Y$	0.14 ^{**}

^{**} $P < 0.01$

^{*} $P < 0.05$

Table 5 Relationships between IVW and socio-economic features

5.0 Discussion and Conclusions

The first visual walkability model for the city of Johannesburg in South Africa has been developed using machine learning and street view imagery to examine the relationship between social inequalities and visual walkability. The study revealed that vulnerable groups experience a lack of access to well-designed urban areas and endure poor walking conditions, highlighting the presence of multiple inequalities in the context of South Africa. Recognising the importance of active transport in promoting socio-economic activities, these results offer valuable guidance for tailoring transport policies aimed at improving the walking conditions in the city's most marginalized regions. For instance, the model can assist in identifying and prioritising areas needing pedestrian infrastructure improvement based on the proposed IVW indicators, thereby potentially reducing further social inequalities. Several limitations remain. (1) The pretrained Segformer model struggled to accurately classify all elements, indicating the need for fine-tuning these models in the South African context. (2) The IVW framework could be improved by considering context-based factors like the perception of crime (Oyeyemi et al., 2017). (3) It should be noted that correlation does not mean causation. Thus further research is needed to better disentangle the causal relationship between the built environment and socio-economic deprivations.

6.0 Acknowledgements

We acknowledge Professor Michael Noble from SASPRI for providing SAIMD data and shapefiles of South Africa. Additionally, thanks to Huiying Long from UCL's Global Healthcare Management (Analytics) program, and to Sophia Cheung and Qinke Cai from UCL's Department of Geography for participating in the subjective scoring evaluation.

References

- Arellana, J. et al. (2019). 'Urban walkability considering pedestrians' perceptions of the built environment: a 10-year review and a case study in a medium-sized city in Latin America', *Transport Reviews*, 40(2), pp.183–203. DOI: 10.1080/01441647.2019.1703842.
- Darmofal, D. (2015). 'Spatial Lag and Spatial Error Model', In *Spatial Analysis for the Social Sciences* (pp. 96–118). DOI: 10.1017/CBO9781139051293.007.

Gevisser (2014). *Lost and found in Johannesburg : a memoir / Mark Gevisser*. Granta.

Lloyd,C.D.et.al.(2021).‘Neighbourhood change and spatial inequalities in Cape Town’, *The Geographical Journal*, 187(4), pp.315–330. DOI: 10.1111/geoj.12400.

Lu,J.et.al.(2021).‘Using Street View Imagery and Computer Vision Method for Visual Walkability Measurement in London’, *29th Annual GIS Research UK Conference (GISRUK)*, Cardiff, Wales, UK (Online). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4668683>.

Lu,Y.et.al.(2018).‘The effect of street-level greenery on walking behavior: Evidence from Hong Kong’, *Social Science & Medicine (1982)*, 208, pp.41–49. DOI: 10.1016/j.socscimed.2018.05.022.

Noble,M.et.al.(2013). *Multiple Deprivation and Income Poverty at Small Area Level in South Africa in 2011*. Cape Town: SASPRI.

Oyeyemi,A.L.et.al.(2017).‘Construct Validity of the Neighborhood Environment Walkability Scale for Africa’, *Medicine and Science in Sports and Exercise*, 49(3), pp.482–491. DOI: 10.1249/MSS.0000000000001131.

Wood,A.(2022).‘Problematizing the concept of walkability in Johannesburg’, *Journal of Urban Affairs*, ahead-of-print(ahead-of-print), pp.1–15. DOI: 10.1080/07352166.2022.2043159.

Xie,E.et.al.(2021).*SegFormer: Simple and Efficient Design for Semantic Segmentation with Transformers*. DOI: 10.48550/arxiv.2105.15203.

Yin, L.&Wang, Z.(2016).‘Measuring visual enclosure for street walkability: Using machine learning algorithms and Google Street View imagery’, *Applied Geography (Sevenoaks)*, 76, pp.147–153. DOI: 10.1016/j.apgeog.2016.09.024.

Zhou,H.et.al.(2019).‘Social inequalities in neighborhood visual walkability: Using street view imagery and deep learning technologies to facilitate healthy city planning’, *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 50, pp.101605–. DOI: 10.1016/j.scs.2019.101605.

Zhu,W.et.al.(2013).‘Agent-Based Modeling of physical activity behavior and environmental correlations: An introduction and illustration’, *Journal of Physical Activity & Health*, 10(3), pp.309–322. DOI: 10.1123/jpah.10.3.309.

Biographies

Lingshan Li is a recent graduate of MSc in Social and Geographic Data Science at UCL. She has a background in spatial data analysis, machine learning, urban sustainability and GIS.

Dr. Stephen Law is currently a lecturer (Assistant Professor) in Social and Geographic Data Science in UCL Geography. His research focuses on geographic data science, urban image analysis, urban economics, urban design and space syntax.